

THE NATIONAL CHARACTER OF PHRASEOLOGICAL EXPRESSIONS IN
TRANSLATION AND THEIR REFLECTION IN WORKS OF ART.

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Yusufjonova Shakhlo Mukhtorovna

Fergana State University,
Faculty of Foreign Languages
Department of "German and French languages",
teacher of German language
e-mail: usufzonovasahlo@gmail.com

Abstract: Phraseological units are considered a linguistic unit that makes up the vocabulary of each language. They, as a language unit, are in a state of pre-speech readiness. Also, phraseological units in each language have their own linguistic character. But in all languages, phraseological units serve as the richness of the language.

Keywords: a translator, the author's style, translation, the national character, expressions, context, phraseological units, the meanings of the words

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Since phraseological expressions are often found in a work of fiction in the author's language, as well as in the speech of the characters depicted in it, they are very characteristic of fiction. However, A.M. Fedorov believed that this category of speech means could not be the private property of fiction alone. Because phraseological expressions are also used in journalism and, partly, in scientific literature. Therefore, they should be treated not only as a question concerning fiction, but also as a very important general language issue.

It is known that when a translator waves a pencil on behalf of the author, it means that it reflects the style of the author. Even if one work is translated by ten people with the same artistic ability, ten completely different translations are obtained. This is due to the fact that, first of all, everyone understands the reflection of the author's style in their own way, moreover, the influence of the translator's style is noticeable in any translation, since in N.V.Gogol's works, in the translation of Kahor, the influence of the Kahor style is noticeable, In L.N.Tolstoy's novels, addressed to the Uzbek language, a trace of the Mirzakalon Ismaili pen is known, From the poems and poems of N.A.Nekrasov, read in Uzbek, the "sign" of Mirtemir's creativity follows. But this does not mean that the translator has presented his own style, instead of reflecting the style of the author.

In translation, the reflection of phraseology in the reflection of the national character of the original and the author's style is of great importance. Based on this, some scientists recommend translating phraseological units in the work as their own. In the translation of phraseological units, variations are very common. In the theory of translation, this is considered as a negative phenomenon. In fact, if the

same motif or idiom is translated by several translators with long similar versions of the same combination or in a dry form (such cases occur quite often), this cannot be considered a genuine translation. However, at this point it is worth noting something completely different. Because languages have mutually exclusive phraseological expressions that can be translated in the same way in almost any context. But most phraseological units at all times, not all translators, in any context can give with a certain equivalent or alternative combination, and such a requirement cannot even be put before the translator. Even when each translator reflects the style of the author, this will be a sign of his individual style. This becomes obvious when translating phraseological units. It is impossible to translate the whole work, all the phraseological units in it so that the two translators are absolutely similar to each other. Therefore, when phraseological units are translated by two different translators in accordance with the same context, blaming translators for this means not understanding the specifics of literary translation. Phraseological expressions, like proverbs and sayings, are not just a sum of words, but a product of folk wisdom, its imagination and artistic fantasy. These expressions, which have a special populist character, not only reflect the characteristics of the Creator people, the country, but also have a strong influence on the formation of phraseology of many languages of the world. Therefore, the one who reaps them must belong to both folk cultures and be aware of their linguistic richness. Translation is an art in which the translation of a word or phrase cannot simply be taken from a dictionary and transferred to a second text. In many cases, the dictionary becomes powerless to express the event or situation described in the text.

Such phraseological units are common both in colloquial speech and in fiction. In the process of translation, we often come across such texts. Phraseology is a stable in its composition and structure, lexically indivisible untranslatable and valuable dictionary, acting as a separate lexical unit. Translation of phraseological units from language to language is a very complex branch of phraseology that requires a lot of experience in studying this discipline. Another important feature of phraseological units is that the meaning of each of them does not merge with the meanings of the words included in it. Therefore, phraseological units are designated by the Greek term "idiom", which means "specific". In English, they are also called "idioms". Some linguists initially argued that phraseological units cannot be translated into other languages. Currently, in order to make the art of translation more attractive, linguists use historical data, ethnography, reflecting not only the evidence of the languages of the present and the past, but also the peculiarities of the life of the people. Researchers should know the customs and

customs of people, their beliefs and superstitions, as this helps to determine the origin of phraseology. Their content side is phraseological meaning.

Polysemous phraseological units serve to enrich the vocabulary of language and speech and embody the meanings of emotional coloring. Therefore, we must be able to correctly use homonyms of phraseological units at the time of translation. Only then will we be able to achieve great success in the field of translation.

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